

Bank Customers' Perspective on Deposits Mobilized Through Digital Marketing

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Introduction

Deposit mobilization is an integral part of banking activity. It is one of the main functions of banking business and so an important source of working fund for the bank. Deposit mobilization is the collection of cash or funds from the public through its current, savings, fixed, recurring accounts and other banks specialized schemes. Bank deposits provide secured investment options to the investors. Today, the banking sector is adopting new dimensions in mobilizing deposits through digital marketing. Digital Marketing uses digital channels such as websites, Search Engine, social media, mobile apps and email for promoting and advertising bank products and services.

Objectives

- To present an overview about the role of digital marketing in deposit mobilization in banks.
- To analyse the merits and demerits of deposit mobilization through digital marketing from the view point of customers.
- To suggest few strategies to enhance deposit mobilization through digital marketing.

Review of Literature

Bittner et.al. (2007) stated that service innovation is less disciplined and less creative in the service sector when compared to manufacturing and technology sector. Service innovation in banking sector requires involvement of human behaviour.

Narayana Maharana et.al (2015) in the article "Deposit mobilization of commercial banks: A Comparative Study of BOB and Axis bank in Bhubaneswar City" emphasized that banks should concentrate on security issues when deposits are raised through online.

Methodology

Literature provides the base about the concept and but effect is still unclear. The present analytical study is based on primary data collected from 100 respondents who had deposited funds in the

form of fixed deposits in banks and are residing in and around Chennai. The primary data was collected through questionnaire. The secondary data is collected from Books, journals, magazines and websites. Tool like percentage analysis was used to compute the research analysis.

Role of Digital Marketing in Deposit Mobilization

Digital marketing is opening a window of opportunities for bank to customer market to promote bank products and services. Digital marketing provides varieties of marketing channels like websites, e-mail social media, search engine optimization, mobile and display ads for promoting banks product and services. Digital marketing has enabled banks to reach customers anytime anywhere at nominal costs. It has attracted new prospects for bankers and has boosted up business of bankers. It has also enabled the customers to understand the various bank deposit schemes without visiting the branch. Social media has also played a vital role in motivating the customers to channelize the savings into deposits.

Analysis and Interpretation

Gender Distribution

Gender	No.of. Respondents	Percentage
Male	65	65
Female	35	35
Total	100	100

It is inferred from the above table that 65% of the respondent were male and 35% of the respondent were female.

Age Distribution: 33% of the respondents were between the age group of 25- 35 years. 27% of the respondents were below 25 years. 12% of the respondents were above 55 yrs.

Qualification: Majority of the respondents were undergraduates (51%). The respondents who were post graduate were 31% and 11% were professionals and 7 % of the respondents did not have any collegiate qualification.

Literacy Level In Computer

The respondents literacy levels in computing skills were assessed and it exhibited 62% of the respondents were average, 36% of the respondents were above average & 2% were below average.

Monthly Income

Particulars	No.of.respondents	Percentage
Below Rs.25,000	20	20
Rs.25, 000 - Rs.50,000	40	40
Rs.50, 000 - Rs.75,000	30	30
Rs.75, 000 - Rs.1,00,000	10	10
Above Rs.1,00,000	10	10

It is inferred from the above Table 40% of the respondents were between the monthly income of Rs.25,000 to Rs.50,000, 30% of respondents were between Rs.50,000- Rs.75,000 , 20% of the respondent were below an income of Rs.25,000 and the rest was equally shared between the income groups of Rs.75,000 - Rs.1,00,000 and above Rs.1,00,000.

Regular Habit of Saving Income in Bank Deposits

It was surprising to note that 58% of respondents had regular habit of saving income in the form of bank deposits, 22% of the respondents remained neutral and 20% did not have the a regular habit of saving income in the form of bank deposits.

Nature of Banks

51% of respondents had deposited in private sector banks, 42% of respondents made deposit in public sector Banks and 7% in foreign bank.

Investments Through Digital Marketing

62% of the respondents had invested deposit through digital marketing, 8% remained neutral and 30% of the respondents had not invested through digital marketing.

Digital Marketing Modes that Attracted Deposits

Bank websites was the top most digital mode with 33% that attracted the investors to make bank deposits. SMS from bank stood next with 20% and E-Mail with 16% motivated the investors to make bank deposits. Advertisement through social media ranked next with 12%, which was followed by search engine optimization with 10%. Pop- up –ads motivated the investors to a very less extent in making bank deposits.

Advantages of Depositing Funds Through Digital Marketing

The top three advantages of making deposits through digital Marketing was time saving with 29%, any time anywhere banking with 27%, flexibility in deposit schemes with 18%. Quick transfer of funds with 16% was considered as the next benefit. It was followed by immediate notification from Banks and saving money without wasting time in travelling cost with 4%.

Challenges in Digital Marketing

The respondents felt technical issues (30%) was the major challenge in depositing funds through digital marketing. The respondents stated digital marketing posed cyber frauds with 23% due to fraudulent e -mail and hacking. Fear of losing money and lack of trust was next challenge with 15% in depositing money in digital marketing. The next major challenge was lack of personal interactions and face to face conversations with bankers with 10%. Some of the respondents considered not possessing adequate computing skills with 9% were the challenge in depositing funds through digital marketing. It was followed by difficulty in understanding the deposit schemes and lack of awareness by 7% and 6% respectively.

Findings

- 65% of the respondent were male and 35% of the respondent were female which showed male invest in fixed deposit through digital marketing than female.
- Majority of the respondents who invested through digital mode were between 25-35 years.
- Majority of the respondents were undergraduates and their computer literacy level was average.
- Majority of the respondents 40% of the respondents were between the monthly income of Rs.25, 000 to Rs. 50,000 and 30% of respondents were between Rs. 50,000- Rs. 75,000.
- More than 50% of respondents had regular habit of savings income through fixed deposits and 62% of the respondents had invested through digital marketing.
- The depositors stated that the private bank attracted fixed deposits than public sector banks.

- Bank websites was the top most digital mode with 33% that attracted the investors to make bank deposits. SMS from bank stood next with 20% and E-Mail with 16% motivated the investors to make bank deposits.
- The top three advantages of making deposits through digital Marketing was time saving with 29%, any time anywhere banking with 27% and flexibility in deposit schemes with 18%.
- The respondents felt technical issues (30%) was the major challenge in depositing funds through digital marketing. The respondents stated digital marketing posed cyber frauds with 23% due to fraudulent e -mail and hacking. Fear of losing money and lack of trust was next challenge with 15% in depositing money in digital marketing.

Suggestions

- Banks should create awareness about E-banking to the existing customers and to the prospective customers.
- Banks can place few kiosks and carry out few demos in order to attract deposits through digital mode.
- Banks should concentrate on cyber security issues and enhance the confidence of the customers to deposit money through digital channels.
- Banks can organize awareness campaigns, customer day celebration to overcome the fear of the customers and motivate them to deposit money through digital mode.
- Banks should solve complaints regarding technical issues immediately once it receives communication from the customers.
- Banks can send secured OTPs and create awareness about cyber begging and improve its server in order to prevent cyber frauds indulged by fraudsters.
- Banks can make the apps and websites user friendly so that everyone can access easily without any difficulties.
- Banks can use paid search marketing channels and social media platform like facebook and linked in effectively to enhance the customer base of depositing funds through digital mode. technologies like data analytics, block chain, cognitive banking can be used to attract and retain depositors.
- Cash back schemes and reward points can be introduced to attract depositors through digital mode.

Conclusion

Usage of multiple digital marketing channels, ensuring cyber security, educating bank customers, improving online and mobile platform by banks can definitely help in enhancing deposits through digital marketing.

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